

The Sound of Fear:
History and Methodology of Horror Film Scoring

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The horror movie genre is rich in complexity, blending design, story, and sensory elements to evoke fear and challenge the viewer's psyche. While visual techniques exploit psychological fears through gruesome and captivating imagery, one of the most powerful tools in horror is the use of sound and music to build tension and emphasize horrific scenes. From the usage of drums to imitate a pounding heartbeat to strings playing harsh, discordant, and unexpected sounds meant to mimic the screams of frightened animals and the crashing, staccato chords that strike into instinctive fears, the composer/film scorer of the horror genre plays a vital role in delivering the full effect of the film that often goes unnoticed.

A few primary concepts in music theory must be understood to comprehend the score's development and musical style fully. The first and most key concept is the idea of intervals and their qualities, which is one of the most used tactics to create feelings of tension and instability. In traditional Western music, there are 12 notes: A, A#/Bb, B, C, C#/Db, D, D#/Eb, E, F, F#/Gb, G, and G#/Ab (where the '/' represents two spellings for the same frequency. Note the lack of enharmonic/same sounding notes as E#/F or Fb/E, and B#/C or Cb/B). The distance between each note, linearly in respect to the list in order, is referred to as a half-step (A to A#), with a whole step being two half-steps between notes (A to B). The number of steps between each note determines its interval quality. If the distance between two notes is a "perfect" interval, it is called perfect consonance. Consonant intervals that exhibit major or minor qualities are known as imperfect consonant intervals – either a 3rd or a 6th, as these determine the quality of a chord (see Table 1). The rest are classified as dissonant intervals – the most harmonically unstable – and are generally used for building tension within a piece of music to resolve it to a more stable note.

Table 1

Qualities of consonant and dissonant intervals and their distance (in half-steps)

<u>Perfect Consonance</u>	<u>Imperfect Consonance</u>	<u>Dissonance</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perfect 1 (Unison) • Perfect 8 (Octave) • Perfect 4th • Perfect 5th 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major 3rd • Minor 3rd • Major 6th • Minor 6th 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major 2nd • Minor 2nd • Major 7th • Minor 7th • Augmented 4th/Diminished 5th
<p><u>Distances:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P1, d2 = 0 half-steps • m2, A1 = 1 half-step • M2, d3 = 2 half-steps • m3, A2 = 3 half-steps • M3, d4 = 4 half-steps • P4, A3 = 5 half-steps • A4, d5 = 6 half-steps • P5, d6 = 7 half-steps • m6, A5 = 8 half-steps • M6, d7 = 9 half-steps • m7, A6 = 10 half-steps • M7, d8 = 11 half-steps • P8, A7 = 12 half-steps 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perfect (P) • Major (M) • Minor (m) • Augment (A) • Diminished (d)

These dissonant intervals are especially used in horror movies, with consonant intervals being rarer. Particularly touched upon is the “tritone,” the interval of a raised (augmented) 4th/lowered (diminished) 5th. These generally perfect intervals separate the most dissonant note in the musical scale – and leaping between notes through a tritone creates extreme tension and

confusion harmonically, as it creates the sense that the root (or bottom note) of the interval is rootless. Intervals can also be used to form a scale – a series of notes (generally 7) are laid out through a pattern of whole and half steps beginning with a note of choice (the key center). These take up qualities called a “mode,” such as major, minor, or diminished scales. These different forms of musical scales have varying sonorities of their own, with major being the most consonant, of course, the most avoided in horror films, minor being imperfect consonant generally, and the diminished scale being the most harmonically unstable. This type of rarely-used scale is highly seen in film scores, as all of the chords in the scale have no sense of clear resolution and continuously build tension.

Chords in traditional Western music are 3 (or more) notes played simultaneously, usually being a triad (A root note, its 3rd, and 5th) or a 7th chord (A root note, its 3rd, 5th, and 7th). Specific interval patterns form these musical structures to form varying qualities, with major and minor being the most harmonically stable and augmented and especially diminished being the most dissonant and yearning for resolution (see Table 2). Different chords based on various notes of the scale have varying quality and different functions (which chord in the scale should the current chord lead to) as well. They can also be inverted (rearranged and stacked up by putting different notes of the chord as the root) to create varying amounts of tension in the chord, allowing for different sonorities. Among the family of musical scales, however, is the chromatic scale, which includes all 12 Western notes with no clear key center. Film watchers of any kind should be familiar with this scale – the sound of a single-stringed instrument or horn continuously rising in pitch with no break between notes (similar to a Shepard Tone). The instability of chromaticism is a key feature in any horror movie, especially due to its lack of chords that naturally and harmonically appear, creating no possible clear resolutions.

Table 2

Chord qualities by interval (root position)

<u>Triad</u>	<u>7th Chord</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major: M3/m3 • Minor: m3/M3 • Diminished: m3/m3 • Augmented: M3/M3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Major Major: M3/m3/M3 • Major Minor: M3/m3/m3 • Minor: m3/M3/m3 • Half Diminished: m3/m3/M3 • Fully Diminished: m3/m3/m3

Joseph Scheurer reviews the general recurring motifs (A small group of notes repeated through a piece to form a short musical idea) of classic horror films, including ones such as life vs. death, secular vs. supernatural, human normality vs. alien abnormality, normal sexual vs. abnormal sexuality, social order vs. disorder, and health vs. disease. Prominent of these typical conflicts, Scheurer concludes through analysis of horror film music, is the struggle between an “individual (as a person and concept) involved in a struggle with [some form of] a monster who is a threat to/byproduct of social institutions and/or the individual’s identity.” Composers follow these same ideas for use in underscoring these types of conflicts and emphasizing themes for dramatic personification. One can draw upon these ideas to create musical phrases (units of musical meter that have a complete musical sense of their own, built from motifs to form melody lines and other large sections in a piece) that signify instability, abnormality, and dysfunction.

By following the motif of the film and recreating that in the score, composers can create varying forms of tension that fit the scene and personify the moods and actions currently on the screen. These ideas are drawn predominantly from classical (generally orchestral) music with high-pitched, plucked strings, dissonant chords on brass, extremely dissonant and unusual interval leaps,

and mixtures of diatonic and atonal phrases. Also common are musical phrases in three note patterns, descending or alternately descending and ascending.

Through deep score analysis, one can see Stephen Sondheim's work in scoring the musical thriller "Sweeney Todd" and his aim for it to feel like a horror film by drawing upon Classical Hollywood film scoring (McGill 2). The film adaptation follows the original score nearly identical as well. In his composition style, orchestration based on classical practices was used to sustain musical tension between numbers and give clues to the drama. Through the use of abnormal harmonic structures, electronic sounds, and loud, crashing organ phrases, Sondheim aimed to create a dark, Gothic-style horror feeling. Music was designed to be "unsettling, scary, and very romantic." He draws on suspense sequences in movies and their use of keeping the music going at all times; this was done throughout the entire musical to keep the audience in a constant state of tension, keeping them engaged at all times and bridging the division between the theater (as a location) and the stage.

According to McGill, approximately eighty percent of the score is sung, and the rest is entirely underscored. His primary influence follows film composer Bernard Herrmann and his use of the "Herrmann" (Generally the half-diminished 7th) chord. Sondheim also based his compositions on silent film music, which had been used as a means of blotting out distractions such as other people, projectors, chairs, and so on, which had evolved into a way to create emotional and dramatic cues for the events on the stage. Among this, he also followed ideas of nineteenth-century opera, of which composer Richard Wagner (1843-51) had developed the technique of tying musical themes to specific characters and/or situations.

Director Stanley Kubrick is especially known for his use of primarily concert music in his films, drawn from all periods of classical music as far back as the 13th century and as recent as

1973 (Lionnet 44). Original scores were rare in Kubrick's films past 1968, including in "The Shining" and "Rocky Mountains," which had been originally scored but were minimal and played a traditional role in the movies. One piece, "Blue Danube Waltz" by Johann Strauss, contains a single G in an ostinato throughout the entire piece. This style left a haunting mark on its audience because of the tension created by the music never pausing.

According to Lionnet, the only piece actually credited by title is Béla Bartók's "Music for Strings, Percussion and Celesta," of which six of the nine tracks of the film's soundtrack come from, and only two other composers are credited by name: György Ligeti, and Krzysztof Penderecki. Wendy Carlos, the composer responsible for the original scores of the film, complements these classical composers' works through re-orchestration using a Moog synthesizer, with haunting, shrill voices and other harsh aural effects. Kubrick had only altered endings of these pieces when creating cuts in the film, keeping the scenes synched with the music rather than vice versa; this is consistent with his other films, such as "A Clockwork Orange," where most of the second movement of Beethoven's "Ninth Symphony" appears. The study of the music of *The Shining* is complex; however, the soundtrack that was released in 1980 concurrently with the movie was withdrawn soon after its release due to copyright issues and lack of crediting. Lionnet adds that "the working materials, including the recordings of concert pieces, are the property of the Kubrick estate and not available to the public for research," making research on the film and its score increasingly difficult.

Neil Lerner, a professor of musicology who specializes in music of the United States and the history and analysis of music and cinema, touches upon such subjects as the development of modern horror film scoring, beginning as far back as silent films which had used music for cues to produce effects that upheld the feelings of the scenes, such as strange, grotesque, and storm

music as well. These were also carried throughout the 1900s as Hollywood's studio system grew and new composers emerged. Also discussed are ideas such as music-free dialogue and dialogue-free music in more contemporary movies such as "Psycho" and its use of musical cues and audiovisual representations. Other composers are noted for their use of chants and nursery rhymes for movies, as well as sonic, progressive, and experimental music; among these music forms also includes the sonic style of musique concrete. Lerner discusses that the organ is an essential instrument in film scoring, and its placement in the music serves as a "disorienting force for the audience," and that many contemporary composers rely heavily on the use of electronic and synthesized sounds: this particularly includes John Carpenter's use of 1970's keyboards. Carpenter's usage of these keyboards allows for "[the creation of] an eerie atmosphere through the use of starkness and repeated phrasing and themes, combined with the techniques of superimposition and displacement" (Lerner 68).

Author Joseph Stannard discusses the innovations of contemporary horror-film composers and their attempts to rewrite the rules of previous composers such as Bernard Herrmann. Some examples include early forms of synthesizers, hammered sheets of metal, and other electronics that create a sense of clatter and chaos to create tension in the score. Other, more recent methods are portrayed in audio manipulation, such as Christopher Young and his use of orchestral samples – audio samples of traditional instruments sampled and manipulated to become unrecognizable: warped, fragmented, and demonic. Some recent composers have also done the same but instead by using human vocals as their primary sound sample, including Jonathan Snipes, who designed his score for "Contracted: Phase 2" to sound human: using sounds of illness such as stuffiness, snorting, and coughing, to create a diseased and industrial sound; these aural effects are known as diegetic sounds (which also include music represented as coming from instruments in the story

space, a.k.a. source music), with non-diegetic sounds generally being background music or effects (see Table 3). A film scorer can use the two different types of sounds to create sonorities representing ambiguity and surprise through the proper mixture. According to authors Thomppson Bordwell and Millar Reize, the distinction between diegetic and non-diegetic sound depends on our understanding of film viewing and listening conventions. Another score in his repertoire was designed to replicate the terrifying feelings of sleep paralysis through the use of “hellish” white noise.

Table 3

Diegetic and non-diegetic sounds

<u>Diegetic Sound</u>	<u>Non-Diegetic Sound</u>
<p>Sound whose source is visible on the screen or whose source is implied to be present by the action of the film:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • voices of characters • sounds made by objects in the story <p>Diegetic sound is any sound presented as originating from a source within the film’s world [and] can be either on screen or off screen depending on its source within or outside the frame.</p>	<p>Sound whose source is neither visible on the screen nor has been implied to be present in the action:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • narrator’s commentary • sound effects, which are added for the dramatic effect • mood music <p>Non-diegetic sound is represented as coming from a source outside the story space.</p>

Source: Thomppson, Bordwell and Millar, Reize. “Diegetic Sound.” *FilmSound*. Accessed 16 April 2018.

Though film composers are far less known than movie directors, the importance of their roles is highly definite. Proper composition of these complex scores requires extreme amounts of creativity and a strong background in music theory. In such cases of complexity, especially in live performances and those transcribed into films like “Sweeney Todd,” the composer must create lengthy scores that match up directly to the actors while also developing important pieces of the film, such as the atmosphere and creating tension and confusion. With the advancements in modern technology and the increase in study of these composition methods, among developments in human psychology, film scores of all types have become an increasingly complex yet creative subject that has an undying role in the movie industry and the role of the composer has become increasingly more important.

Work Cited

- Bordwell, Thompsson and Reize, Millar. "Diegetic Sound." *FilmSound*, www.filmsound.org/terminology/diegetic.htm. Accessed 27 March 2018.
- Lerner, Neil. "Terror Tracks: Music, Sound and Horror Cinema/Music in the Horror Film: Listening to Fear." *Journal of Film Music*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2011, pp. 65–68.
- Lionnet, Leonard. "Music Unveiled: Mysteries of the Overlook: Unraveling Stanley Kubrick's Soundtrack for *The Shining*;" *Fil Score Monthly*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2004, pp. 44–47.
- McGill, Craig M. "'It Might Have Been Sophisticated Film Music': The Role of the Orchestra in Stage and Screen Versions of *Sweeney Todd, the Demon Barber of Fleet Street*." *Studies in Musical Theatre*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2014, pp. 5–26.
- Scheurer, Timothy E. *Music and Mythmaking in Film: Genre and the Role of the Composer*. McFarland & Company, 2008, pp. 176–204
- Stannard, Joseph. "The Music of the Fears." *Sight and Sound*, vol. 27, no. 4, 2017, pp. 58–59.